

A Case of Cytomegalovirus-Induced Acute Progressive Outer Retinal Necrosis in a Young GirlPiyush Jain¹, Sarita Panda², Ankita Mishra³, Deepika Priyadarshini⁴, Sabita Devi⁵, Reikhongul Rangla⁶¹Junior Resident, Department of Ophthalmology, Maharaja Krushna Chandra Gajapati Medical College, Berhampur, Odisha India²Head of Department, Department of Ophthalmology, Maharaja Krushna Chandra Gajapati Medical College, Berhampur, Odisha India³Junior Resident, Department of Ophthalmology, Maharaja Krushna Chandra Gajapati Medical College, Berhampur, Odisha India⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Maharaja Krushna Chandra Gajapati Medical College, Berhampur, Odisha India⁵Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Maharaja Krushna Chandra Gajapati Medical College, Berhampur, Odisha India⁶Senior Resident, Department of Ophthalmology, Maharaja Krushna Chandra Gajapati Medical College, Berhampur, Odisha India

Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

This case report presents a 7-year-old girl with acute retinal necrosis (ARN) secondary to suspected viral infection. The patient presented with decreased vision, pain, and a history of fever, headache, and hearing loss. Despite previous treatment for uveitis, the patient's condition deteriorated, leading to severe inflammation and vision loss in the right eye. The left eye also showed signs of involvement. The case highlights the importance of early diagnosis and prompt management of ARN to prevent further visual impairment.

Keywords: Acute Retinal Necrosis (ARN), Viral Infection, Uveitis, Retinitis, Choroiditis, Vision Loss, Pain, Fever, Headache, Hearing Loss, Case Report, Paediatric Ophthalmology, Cytomegalovirus.

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Introduction

ARN is a rare disease that is caused mainly by Herpes simplex virus (HSV) or Varicella zoster virus (VZV) [1,2], but also Cytomegalovirus (CMV) and Epstein-Barr virus (EBV) infections may be etiologic factors of ARN [2,3].

The most common clinical signs of ARN are: arteritis and periphlebitis of the retinal and choroidal vasculature, confluent necrotizing retinitis affecting the peripheral retina and moderate to severe vitritis [4,5]. Anterior granulomatous uveitis is universal and unless the fundus is examined the diagnosis may be missed. The intraocular inflammation resolves within 4-12 weeks, leaving necrotic retina with retinal pigment epithelium atrophy. The fellow eye becomes involved in 30-50% of patients, usually within 2 months [6,7].

Case report: This is a case presentation of A 7-year-old girl presented to the ophthalmology

outpatient department with painless diminution of vision in the right eye, more than the left eye, for 50 days which was associated with past history of fever, headache, hearing loss. She had a past history of uveitis of suspected viral etiology since 2month for which she was under medication.

Her visual acuity in right eye was PLPR inaccurate with (Near Vision) NV <N36 left eye was 6/60 with NV- N18. Pupils are mid dilated and fixed. Intraocular pressure was 16 mmHg in (Right Eye) RE and 15mmhg in (Left Eye) LE. Slit lamp examination revealed RE severe inflammatory response and LE mild inflammatory response in AC, cornea was clear in (Both Eyes) BE.

Posterior segment shows vitreous haze 1+, disc pallor, arterioles attenuation, multiple whitish yellow inflammatory lesion in mid-periphery.

Figure 1: Right eye fundus showing disc pallor, arteriolar attenuation, and multiple whitish-yellow necrotic lesions in the mid-peripheral retina.

Figure 2: Left eye fundus picture showing disc pallor, arterioles attenuation, multiple whitish yellow necrotic lesion in mid peripheral of Retina mostly in the inferior quadrant

Patient underwent additional laboratory tests like serum screening for the presence of antibodies against HSV, EBV, VZV, HIV, which were negative and also CMV which gave positive results. CBC shows leucocytosis, ESR was raised. MRI of Central nervous system and CSF study was unremarkable.

Treatment with intravenous acyclovir 10mg/kg 8hourly for 10 days with additional systemic steroids (Prednisolone 1mg/ kg/ day), and aspirin (500 mg/ day), was initiated. Patient also received one dose of intraocular Gancyclovir. Steroids were started a few days after the initiation of antiviral therapy. During a follow-up period intraocular inflammation and retinitis decreased and patient was converted to oral Gancyclovir 5 x 800 mg/ day for 10 weeks. The total regression of the retinal inflammatory lesion in the left eye was observed and the vision improvement. However in the right

eye, despite the inflammation resolution the vision didn't improved.

Discussion

In spite of characteristic clinical signs, the diagnosis of ARN may be difficult in some cases because the clinical presentation may range from focal to extensive involvement and the clinical course may be mild or fulminating [9,10]. The following conditions should be considered in differential diagnosis of ARN: CMV retinitis, progressive outer retinal necrosis (PORN), Syphilitic neuroretinitis, *Candida albicans* endophthalmitis, acute multifocal haemorrhagic retinal vasculitis, sarcoidosis, atypical peripheral toxoplasmatic retinochoroiditis and Behçet syndrome [1,8,9].

Confirmation of the diagnosis through PCR is recommended to improve the medical management

and prevent fellow eye involvement and disease progression with an increased risk of complications [11]. One can start anti-infectious therapy first and then begin steroids [13]. In our patient systemic steroids were induced three days after the antiviral therapy was initiated. Steroids are indicated in severe cases with optic nerve involvement and marked vitritis [1,12]. If there is sight-threatening retinitis or there is the involvement of the optic disc or macula (zone 1), intravitreal injections should be performed. Ganciclovir can be given at 2 mg per 0.1 mL, and foscarnet can be given 1.2 mg to 2.4 mg per 0.1 mL [13]. The prognosis in ARN is relatively poor, with 60% of patients having a final visual acuity of less than 6/60 as a result of complications such as traction or rhegmatogenous retinal detachment and optic nerve involvement [1,8].

Conclusion

The diagnosis and management of ARN are complex and only a Prompt recognition and early treatment of ARN can prevent severe visual loss, particularly in pediatric patients. Healthcare workers including the nurse practitioner and primary care physicians who see patients with herpes simplex or any viral infection of the eye should immediately refer these patients to an ophthalmologist. Immediate treatment of the patient is required and can be done in either the inpatient or outpatient setting. The goal is to decrease the incidence in the fellow eye.

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